

MATRIX CRACKING IN CERAMIC MATRIX
COMPOSITES UNDER QUASI-STATIC TENSILE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The quasi-static tensile behaviour of unidirectional, $(0/90)_s$, $(0_2/90_4)_s$ and $(0/90)_{3s}$ Silicon carbide fibre (Nicalon) reinforced calcium aluminosilicate glass ceramic matrix laminates is described. The damage development is quantified by counts of matrix crack density (in both the longitudinal and transverse plies) and stiffness reduction as functions of applied strain. The damage initiation and growth are discussed with reference to Aveston, Cooper, Kelly (ACK) theory for the unidirectional ply cracking and crossply laminate shear-lag theory (originally developed for polymer matrix composites) for the transverse ply cracking behaviour.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Ceramic matrix; Quasi-static testing; Matrix cracking; Stiffness loss.

1. INTRODUCTION

The mechanical behaviour of continuous fibre ceramic matrix composites has been the subject of much theoretical and, more recently, experimental research. There are already in the literature a number of models which consider the matrix cracking behaviour of unidirectional fibre reinforced brittle matrix materials loaded parallel to the fibre direction e.g. [1,2,3,4]. To model transverse ply cracking in crossply (i.e. 0/90 type) ceramic matrix composites it should be possible to make use of existing models developed for polymer matrix systems. Experimental data in the literature enabling such models to be tested are limited, although there are a number of studies which describe and interpret the basic mechanical behaviour of both unidirectional and crossply laminates e.g. [5,6,7]. In the present work we present experimental observations on unidirectional and a range of crossply ceramic matrix composites and apply simple models to interpret the observed behaviour.

2. MATERIAL AND LAY-UPS

The materials used in the present work were Nicalon (trademark of the Nippon Carbon Company) SiC fibre reinforced calcium aluminosilicate glass-ceramic matrix laminates manufactured by hot pressing pre-preg. Basic properties are shown in Table 1. The lay-ups supplied (courtesy of Rolls-Royce plc) were $(0)_{12}$, $(0/90)_s$, $(0_2/90_4)_s$ and $(0/90)_{3s}$. The nominal ply thickness was 0.18 mm, although this varied by about 10 % from lay-up to lay-up. By dissolving the glass matrix using hydrofluoric acid and by image analysis, the fibre volume fraction was determined as 34 %.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

Tensile coupons 80 mm by 20 mm were cut from the laminates. Both edges of the coupons were polished carefully and, as can be seen from Figures 2 and 3, a high grade of finish was obtained. Due to the weak nature of the fibre matrix bond some damage to fibres in longitudinal plies was incurred, but this did not limit the assessment of matrix damage under subsequent mechanical loading. Abraded and etched aluminium end tags were bonded onto specimens for ease of gripping in Instron wedge grips. Quasi-static tests were carried out using an Instron 1175 under displacement control at a crosshead speed of 0.05 mm/min. Longitudinal and transverse strains were measured using strain gauges so that the modulus and Poisson's ratio could be determined. Some specimens were loaded continuously to failure giving initial tangent values of modulus and Poisson's ratio. Other specimens were used in 'discontinuous tests' in which they were loaded to progressively higher strain levels in order to study damage development. These tests also enabled the progressive changes in stiffness properties with applied strain (and extent of damage) to be determined. Direct observations of matrix cracking were made using optical and scanning electron microscopy (detecting back-scattered electrons) of the polished coupon edges. Crack densities were determined by counting the number of cracks within a known gauge-length.

4. STRESS/STRAIN BEHAVIOUR AND DAMAGE OBSERVATIONS

4.1. Unidirectional Laminate The basic mechanical properties for the $(0)_{12}$ laminate are summarised in Table 2. A typical stress-strain curve, Figure. 1, displays a well-defined 'knee' at about 0.08 % applied strain, which corresponds to the onset of matrix damage. This type of discontinuity and the general shape of the stress-strain curve have been observed for other CMC systems [5,8]. The matrix damage is in the form of an array of cracks spanning the width and thickness of the laminate, see Figure. 2. The stress/strain curve becomes linear again at about 0.3 %, suggesting that matrix cracking has 'saturated' (ie. become constant) by this stage and this was confirmed by crack counting (see next section). Final fracture of the laminate (involving fibre failure) occurs at a strain of about 0.8 %.

4.2. (0/90) Laminates Figure. 1 also shows stress/strain curves for the various crossply laminates tested and Table 2 gives the basic mechanical properties. The stress/strain curves of the crossply laminates show an initial knee at between 0.02 and 0.04 %, corresponding to matrix cracking in the 90° plies. Cracking in the 90° plies continues with increasing strain, Figure. 3. At higher strains the matrix in the longitudinal plies also cracks. Sometimes the longitudinal ply cracks occur as a result of extension of existing 90° ply cracks into neighbouring 0° plies; they are also seen to form independently, see Figure. 4. The crack density in both transverse and longitudinal plies continues to increase with increasing applied strain until eventually 'saturation' (i.e. constant) crack spacings are observed. Final fracture of all the crossply laminates occurs at strains of 0.63 - 0.65 %, compared to the value of 0.8 % for the unidirectional material.

5. CRACK DENSITY AND STIFFNESS REDUCTION DATA

5.1. Unidirectional Laminate Figure. 5 shows the crack density as a function of applied stress in the (0)₁₂ laminate while Figure. 6 shows the same crack density data plotted as a function of applied strain, in which form it may be compared with the cracking data for the unidirectional plies of the various crossply laminates. Figure. 7 shows the modulus (0.05% secant values) as a function of applied strain. The overall stiffness reductions are large, reflecting the significant contribution made by the matrix to the laminate modulus.

5.2. (0/90) Laminates Figure. 8 shows an example of the crack spacing vs applied stress curves obtained from the transverse plies of crossply laminates. In this case (for the (0/90)_s laminate) the data may be compared with a simple shear-lag model - see discussion. Figure. 9 shows the normalised stiffness (0.02% secant values) of the (0/90)_s laminate as a function of applied strain; note that this stiffness reduction is a result of the combined effects of the 90₂ ply cracking (Figure. 8) and the 0° plies cracking (Figure. 6).

6. DISCUSSION

6.1. Cracking in Unidirectional Laminates Many studies in the literature have attempted to model matrix cracking processes in unidirectional CMCs. The classic paper by Aveston et al (ACK) [1] employs an overall energy balance to obtain an expression for the matrix cracking strain, ϵ_{mu} :

$$\epsilon_{mu} = \left[\frac{12\tau\gamma_mE_fV_f^2}{E_fE_m^2rV_m} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (1)$$

where E_m , E_f and E_c are the modulus of the matrix, the fibre and the composite respectively; V_f is the volume fraction of fibre and $V_m (= 1 - V_f)$ is the volume fraction of the matrix; r is the fibre radius. The quantity γ_m is the fracture surface energy of the matrix and τ is the (assumed constant) interfacial shear stress between the fibre and matrix. Matrix cracking continues with no further increase in applied load until there are approximately uniform cracks, spanning the width and thickness of the specimen, spaced

between x' and $2x'$ apart, where

$$x' = \frac{V_m}{V_f} \left[\frac{\sigma_{mu} \Gamma}{2\tau} \right] \quad (2)$$

and σ_{mu} ($= E_m \epsilon_{mu}$) is the fracture stress of the matrix. We can use the above analyses to interpret the data of the present study. The crack density/applied stress data for the unidirectional laminate (Figure. 5) indicate that matrix cracking occurs over a range of applied stress. This is a result of the range of initial flaw sizes which lead to cracks (analysed by [2,3]). The first cracks to go in (at about 0.08 % strain applied i.e. a stress of about 96 MPa) may occur due to the propagation of large pre-existing flaws, while those which occur at progressively higher strains could propagate from smaller pre-existing flaws. The final (or 'saturation') crack spacing in the 0° laminates, $2s_p$, was 0.14 mm. Following [9]

$$2s_f = 1.33x' \quad (3)$$

From equations (1),(2) and (3) using the experimentally determined value of ϵ_{mu} (0.12 %, including thermal strain) and taking $8 \mu\text{m}$ as a representative value for the fibre radius, the inferred values of τ and $2\gamma_m$ are 10 MPa and 6 J m^{-2} respectively. The value of τ is perhaps high while the value of $2\gamma_m$ is reasonable for a ceramic matrix [10]. These calculated values of $2\gamma_m$ and τ enable a 'prediction' to be made for the data of Figure. 5, based on the ACK model. The plot shows clearly that the ACK model is an oversimplification as outlined above. The matrix cracks propagate over a range of applied stress.

6.2. Cracking in (0/90) Laminates Transverse ply cracks increase in density with applied load in a very similar manner to those observed polymer matrix composites. If we assume that the plies of the composite remain bonded and that the response is elastic then we can describe the stress distributions in a cracked (0/90) composite using shear-lag analysis (see e.g. [8]). For a $(0/90)_s$ laminate of longitudinal ply thickness, b , and transverse ply thickness, $2d$, containing a regular array of transverse cracks spaced $2s$ apart the necessary applied stress for further cracking, σ' , is then given by

$$\sigma' = \left[\frac{\sigma_{2u}}{\left[1 - \frac{1}{\cosh \lambda s} \right]} - \sigma_2^T \right] \frac{E_0}{E_2} \quad (4)$$

where E_0 is the rule-of-mixtures modulus of the laminate

($= [bE_1 + dE_2]/[b + d]$), σ_2^T is the initial thermal stress in the transverse ply σ_{2u} is transverse ply strength (assumed constant) and

$$\lambda^2 = \left[\frac{3G_{23}(b + d)E_0}{d^2bE_1E_2} \right] \quad (5)$$

The prediction of equation (8) is compared with the experimental data for 90° cracking in the $(0/90)_s$ laminates in Figure. 8. Agreement with the trends of the data is reasonable. However, there are two main factors which need to be incorporated to improve this type of

model. Firstly the statistical nature of the 90° failure processes needs to be incorporated (perhaps using an approach along the lines of that of [12] for polymer composites). Secondly at high strains the effect of the degradation of the stiffness of the constraining plies (E_1) as a result of their cracking must be considered.

The 'saturation' crack spacings for the 90° plies are summarised in Table 3. For polymer matrix composites it is well established that 'saturation' matrix cracking corresponds to an average crack spacing of the order of the ply thickness e.g. [13]. Overall there is an effect of transverse ply thickness on saturation crack spacing, as would be expected given that the transverse ply thickness influences the rate at which stress is shed back from the 0's into the 90's, but the trend is not well defined for the thinner plies. The 'saturation' crack spacing in the 0° plies of all the laminates seems to tend to the same value, independent of the 0° ply thickness. This is consistent with the model of stress transfer used in the ACK shear-lag analysis i.e. that each fibre interacts with a cylinder of matrix in which it is contained, consequently it is the fibre radius which is the dimension governing stress transfer between fibre and matrix (equation (2)) and the ply thickness has no influence.

7. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The present work has identified and quantified matrix cracking in unidirectional and crossply Nicalon reinforced CAS matrix laminates. Matrix crack development in unidirectional material can be described approximately using the ACK model. It should also be possible to use the ACK model as a basis for modelling the stress/strain behaviour of a cracked laminate and hence for predicting the residual stiffness. For crossply laminates, a simple shear-lag model, which assumes elastic bonding between the plies, describes the trend of the crack multiplication with applied load but needs to be modified to account for (a) the statistical nature of the failure process and (b) the effect of the simultaneous cracking of the 0° plies. With regard to the former there are existing models in the literature for polymer composites which enable statistical effects to be incorporated. The simultaneous cracking of the 0° plies can be included provided that the unidirectional laminates can be modelled because, to a first approximation, the behaviour of the unidirectional plies in a crossply laminate is the same as that of a unidirectional laminate.

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Table. 1 Summary of main matrix, fibre and unidirectional lamina properties (for $V_f = 0.34$).

E_f	Fibre modulus	190 GPa
α_f	Fibre thermal expansion co-efficient	$3.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$
E_m	Matrix modulus	90 GPa
α_m	Matrix thermal expansion co-efficient	$4.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$
E_1	Lamina modulus (parallel to fibres)	128 GPa
E_2	Lamina modulus (perpendicular to fibres)	85-110 GPa*
ν_{12}	Lamina principle Poisson's ratio	0.24
G_{23}	Lamina shear modulus (through-thickness)	36 GPa#
α_1	Lamina expansion co-efficient (parallel to fibres)	$4.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$
α_2	Lamina expansion co-efficient (perpendicular to fibres)	$4.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$

* Range of values estimated from (0/90) data using laminated plate theory

Estimated assuming 2-3 plane is isotropic and using $G_{23} = E_2/2(1 + \nu_{23})$, taking $\nu_{23} = 0.25$.

Table. 2 Initial moduli, moduli at failure, failure strengths and failure strains for $(0)_{12}$, $(0/90)_s$, $(0/90)_{3s}$ and $(0_2/90_4)_s$ laminates.

LAMINATE	INITIAL MODULUS* (GPa)	POISSON'S RATIO*	ϵ_f^+ (%)	σ_u^+ (MPa)	FINAL TANGENT MODULUS ⁺ (GPa)
$(0)_{12}$	128±7	0.24±0.03	0.78	400	39
$(0/90)_s$	120±20	0.24±0.07	0.63	173	13
$(0_2/90_4)_s$	101±16	0.20±0.03	0.65	107	8
$(0/90)_{3s}$	110±5	0.22±0.05	0.63	146	12

* Mean of at least five specimens

+ One specimen only

Table. 3 Summary of cracking thresholds (from extrapolating crack density/applied strain curves and adding the calculated thermal strain) and saturation crack spacings for laminates tested.

LAMINATE	PLY	THICKNESS (mm)	THRESHOLD CRACKING STRAIN (%)	SATURATION CRACK SPACING (mm)
$(0)_{12}$	0_{12}	2.10	0.12	0.14
$(0_2/90_4)_s$	0_2	0.43	0.10	0.15
$(0/90)_s$	0	0.16	0.14	0.16
$(0/90)_{3s}$	0	0.17	0.08	0.18
$(0_2/90_4)_s$	90_8	1.39	0.03	0.9
$(0/90)_s$	90_2	0.35	0.05	0.25
$(0/90)_{3s}$	90_2	0.36	0.05	0.33
$(0/90)_{3s}$	90	0.18	0.05	0.25

Figure. 1 Stress/strain curve for $(0)_{12}$, $(0/90)_s$, $(0_2/90_4)_s$ and $(0/90)_{3s}$ laminates.

Figure. 2 Typical matrix cracking damage in $(0)_{12}$ laminates.

Figure. 3 Typical transverse ply cracking damage in $(0/90)_s$ laminates.

Figure. 4 Damage in $(0/90)_{3s}$ laminate showing 0° ply cracks, 90° cracks and cracks running across the entire thickness of the laminate.

Figure. 5 Crack density as a function of applied stress in $(0)_{12}$ laminates and prediction of ACK model with $\tau = 10$ MPa, $2\gamma_m = 6$ J m⁻².

Figure. 6 Crack density as a function of applied strain in 0° plies of $(0)_{12}$, $(0/90)_s$, $(0_2/90_4)_s$ and $(0/90)_{3s}$ laminates.

Figure. 7 Normalised stiffness as a function of applied strain in $(0)_{12}$ laminates.

Figure. 8 Crack density as a function of applied stress for 90_2 ply (0.35 mm thick) in $(0/90)_s$ laminate along with prediction of simple shear-lag model, equation (4).

Figure. 9 Normalised stiffness as a function of applied strain in $(0/90)_s$ laminates.